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The Implementation of Maritime Labour Convention in the Ship Management: A Case Study on Risk Management On-Board

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The Maritime Labour Convention (MLC, 2006) is of high importance as other Maritime conventions. It brings some obligations to the biggest parties in the maritime industry which are flag states, port states, seafarers supplying countries and seafarer employing companies. The MLC aims to provide & protect the rights of the seafarers and to maintain their highest standardized living & working areas on board ships by law. The port and flag states have been delegated to inspect the seafarers' employment & working and living standards. Following on the Maritime Labour Convention which was enter into force in August 2013, an established and well-operated risk management system has become compulsory in the ship management system. 985 of 2136 deficiencies, which have been detected by Australian Maritime Safety Authority since 20 August 2013, are related with the obligation in question. From this point of view, it is explicit that risk management is of vital importance for the ship management system.

Herewith this paper, the aim is designated as identifying the expectations of the Convention from the ship management and determining the optimum numerical methods for the best operability risk management model in intense ship working ambience. The accuracy of the model results must be close to the gospel truth. Furthermore, the results have to be the same as in the real industry terms. Since, the effect of a minimum failure, even, may cause huge expenses in shipping industry. Upon the conditions and criterions, the appropriate methods of operational research for risk management model on-board have been selected. Whether the model equiponderates the requirements or not is tested by scenario analysis. All in all, it is proven that the risk management system established herein this study works properly; meanwhile, it is demonstrated that the aforementioned model may be regarded as a notable reference for ship management system.

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INTRODUCTION

International Labour Organization (ILO), has developed The Maritime Labour Convention, 2006 (MLC, 2006) as a fourth pillar of international maritime law; connected with the International Convention for The Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS); the International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping (STCW) and the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution From Ships (MARPOL) [1].

The MLC was developed as a result of a trinity consultation by the delegates of government, employers and worker organizations. The aim of the Convention is to provide detailed rights and safeguards for seafarers and to succeed occupational health and safety protection and prevention arrangements in their working and living areas [2].

MLC came in force internationally as a mandatory instrument on 20 August 2013. Since then, all the ships flying a flag belonging to the whole ratification registered countries have been to meet these mandatory requirements.

The International Labour Organization have authorized the inspector authorities as responsible for applying the regulations of the Convention and its requirements in their ports. One of the most reputable authorities in Tokyo MOU, AMSA proceeded inspections between 20 August 2013 and 31 December 2014. According to Table 1, 2136 deficiencies were issued and 22 vessels were detained in view of MLC. The number of the deficiencies related with each MLC regulations are listed in Table 1 [3].

TABLE 1 HERE

When looked at the Table 1, one can see that %46 of these deficiencies is related with Regulation 4.3. According to Table 1, it is obvious that Regulation 4.3. "Health And Safety Protection And Accident Prevention" on board the shipping vessel

is of vital importance. Thus, this study is dedicated to investigate the optimum solutions to the deficiencies related with this regulation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Zhang and Zhao (2014) who have an article named as "Maritime Labour Policy in China: Restructuring under the ILO's Maritime Labour Convention 2006" have mentioned about the importance of the Convention for Republic of China. Then they have evaluated the convention and procedures and to be established and be integrated into National China Regulations [4].

On their study of Maritime Labour Convention 2006 that has examined Safety Management Documentation Models (2012), Wu and Jeng have developed a model for integration between the convention and business management systems documentation. As a result, they have improved four models named as I model, P model, F model and free model [5].

Startiene (2007) has written up a literature paper about risk analysis and application methods in his paper work. It is seen in his works that five different classification type is generally accepted for risk analysis methods [6].

In his book "International Handbook on Risk Analysis and Management" (2008), Habegger mentions that risk is used by analyst and decision makers such as armed forces, international organizations and joint ventures for following of complex structure trend and development. He evaluates risk analysis as common, financial and insurance [7].

In his book "Fundamentals of Risk Analysis and Risk Management" (1997), Molak edits the theoretical history and academic studies about risk

analysis. He presents model applications for risk management [8].

Ringdahl (2013) examines the concept of the accidents by evaluating the accident events in a system in his book named "Guide to Safety Analysis for Accident Prevention". The book determines methods such as fault tree analysis (FTA), simple event diagram and other decision methods [9].

Maheshwari and Jain's (2014) "Supply Chain Management- Review on Risk Management from Supplier's Perspective" determines to find out various risks from sup-supplier to end consumer at every stage of supply chain and to emphasize extra costs due to the risks [10].

Shapira and March (1987) have prepared an article named "Managerial Perspectives on Risk and Risk Taking" handling the connection link between the risk and decision methods and evaluating risk as gambling and managerial [11].

Wagner (2006) has studied about risk evaluation and employer standardization in fishing sector. The paper emphasizes the importance of risk analysis in fishing and the fact that it is a necessity in European Union's laws [12].

In his master thesis about development of the cabotage transportation and risk analysis of marine accidents in relations (2010), Akyıldız edits marine accidents data in Turkey's marine spaces during the last 10 years and examines the results statistically. Risk assessment was applied for detecting the marine accidents rising due to the development of cabotage transportation and required precautions that prevent marine accidents were determined [13].

Uğurlu (2011) has done a PhD thesis about risk analysis of marine accidents occurs in oil tanker. FTA (Fault Tree Analysis) and ArcMap Geography Information System programs were applied in the thesis to analyze risk assessment form marine accident that occurred between 1998 and 2010 in oil tanker vessels [14]. The marine accidents' data were cited from GISIS (Global Integrated Shipping Information System) formed by IMO (International Maritime Organization).

Alan (2008) prepared a Phd thesis related to risk analysis and safety management model in LNG transportation. The thesis aimed to do risk analysis in LNG and to make a safety management model suggestion. With this model suggestion, it is aimed to increase the power of international competitive companies by enhancing the security standards. Alan (2008) has applied Bayesian Belief Network (BBN) in the study [15].

Özen(2014) has written up a Master's thesis about FMEA (Failure Mode Effect Analysis) application for design of fire, oil and bilge systems in yacht [16].

Eryürek (2003)has done a Phd thesis about the new decision making model in FMEA method. For risk management analysis, ELECTRE method was used in the study [17].

HEALTH AND SAFETY PROTECTION AND ACCIDENT PREVENTION REFERRED TO REGULATION 4.3.IN MARITIME LABOUR CONVENTION

As an auditee, the shipping companies' managements have to provide that the seafarers' labour and living environment on board ships are promoted vocational safety and health in a safe and hygienic atmosphere. When the Regulation 4.3, paragraph 3 in the Convention is reviewed these subjects should be included to the company's management system [2];

(a) the harmony and efficient applications and promotion of vocational safety and health policies and procedures aboard ships that rise the Member's flag, including risk assessment alongside training and directive of seafarers;

(b) logical countermeasures to inhibit vocational accidents, injuries and disease son board ship, including evaluates to diminish and inhibit the risk of exposure to detrimental grades of environmental factors and chemicals along the risk of injury or disease that may result from the using of equipment and machinery on board ships;

(c) on-board programmes for the repression of vocational accidents, injuries and diseases and for continuous improvement in vocational safety and health preservation, involving seafarers' delegates

and all other persons concerned in their application, pursuant to preventive measures, encapsulating engineering and design control, replacement of processes and procedures for mutual and personal duties, and the using of personal protective equipment; and

(d) necessities for inspecting, reporting and correcting unsafe conditions and for prospecting and reporting on-board vocational accidents.

According to this paragraph written in the Regulation 4.3, the shipping company management must define health and safety risks related to the several shipboard activities to which seafarers might fall into. Practices that ensure precautions with the manoeuvre against identified risks are risk evaluation, work permission, behavioral-based safety programs, orientation programs for new seafarers (directed by the ship-owner or manning agency for overall knowledge), and clarifying the ship owners' policies [18]. A successfully established risk management system on board the vessel advances maritime safety including protection of life, health, the marine environment and property by applying risk assessment.

From this point of view, supported by a structured and systematic methodologies "Risk Management System" must be established in ship management system in accordance with this regulation.

RISK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM ONBOARD THE VESSEL

Risk is a measurement of the probability and conclusion of indefinite future cases [19]. Risk assessment is a systematic procedure of determining and evaluation events that could impress the succeeding of objectives, positively or negatively [20].

Risk assessment is a planning tool to assist and provide a logical and sensible consideration of the dangers and risks involved in any task. An effective risk assessment will ensure that those who are going to be involve in the work are fully aware of the risks and all the actions, system and equipment used to minimize the risk.

Hazard, is anything that is potential origin of damage to a precious entity (human, animal, natural, economic, social) [21].

FIGURE 1 HERE

In Figure 1, risk management and mitigation are shown in five stages [22]. These five steps are also advised by International Maritime Organization (IMO) [23]. This flow chart can be adapted to Shipping Company Management System. The process commences with the decision makers describing the problem to be assessed.

The goal of this paper is to establish the most appropriate methods for risk management system in shipping companies. The expectations of working conditions onboard ships are important in establishing a management system. To identify the expectations, the experts of the shipping industries were interviewed and the atmosphere of the ships was observed.

THE EXPECTATIONS OF SHIP WORKING CONDITIONS

Based upon the observation and interviews with the experts, the main expectations of ship working conditions from the risk management models are determined as:

- Practical implementation; the model must be applied in short time
- The outputs of the model must be concrete and applicable
- The outputs operability must be demonstrated by experiences
- The non-operability outputs can be easily eliminated and new outputs can be easily put in the system
- The reliability and preferable levels must be high; the using area must be wide as a proof.
- The requirements of Regulation 4.3. must be compensated.

According to the expectations of ship working conditions detected by the interviews with the experts and the observations; the optimum methods for risk management system for ships are determined and operated with a case study.

Here is the story of the case study. First of all the risks onboard were identified. Secondly, experts' opinions are collected by questionnaire techniques; then, the risk levels were identified by the Failure Mode Effect Analysis. High level risks are investigated by Fault Tree Analyses. Finally, the decision of which precaution would be applied was reached by using Analytical Hierarchy Process.

THE METHODS FOR RISK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The methods used in this study are listed and explained below:

Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA)

FMEA is one of the most popular techniques used for determining the risks [24]. The first formal implementation of FMEA discipline was an renewal of the aerospace industry in the mid-1960s [25]. FMEA has also been the most chosen technique in the other industry branches since the beginning of the designing process for checking security periods. FMEA is an analytical technique that can pave the way for determining the influences of the system component's potential failure types on the system security [5].

Fault Tree Analysis (FTA)

FTA, brings the opportunity for observation about history differed from other techniques [26]. FTA is used for analysis of unexpected situations roots [27]. FTA is especially used in accident analysis to get the reasons of the actions [28]. In this paper, FTA technique is used for analysis of the roots of failures originated from devices onboard ships and human factors.

Analytic Hierarchy Process

AHP is a decision making technique used by the given priority degrees to the decision alternatives and criterions for complex decision problems depending on the management decision making

mechanism [29]. The main steps of the technique are listed below [30]:

- To identify the problems and determine the main goal
- To determine the decision criterions
- To determine the decision alternatives
- To establish hierarchical construction of the problem
- To make double comparison between the criterions and determining the priority levels
- To make double comparison between the alternatives based on criterions and the calculation of the priorities
- To choose the highest priority level from the alternatives

In the Table 2 the significance of the numbers that are used to evaluate the priority of the criterions are given [31]:

TABLE 2 HERE

THE CASE STUDY

The risk management system established with these methods is examined with a case study. According to the subject of the case study; a ship loads a steaming coal in the port of the Samarinda, Indonesia. The loading operation is run offshore by using the floating cranes and barges. Muara Berua, where Samarinda port takes place, is determined as the location. It is identified as intensively piracy attacked area by Global Integrated Shipping Information System (GISIS) [32]. The shipping company management is asked to evaluate the risks and to make a decision against any attack.

According to this scenario, the risks are to be identified the full operation from anchor drop to heave up. Questionnaire and observation techniques are used for identifying the risks through question-answer technique about the operations. The questions are;

- What kind of risks can the anchoring periods in Muara Berau contain from dropping anchor to heaving up the anchor ?

- What is the root of these risks?
- What are the results of these risks?
- What is the amount of damage?
- Which precautions can be taken?

The questionnaire forms are forwarded to 18 ship masters. By the results of these forms, the risks for this operation are determined as;

- Robbery
- Wounding
- Death
- Hijacking
- Taken the Ship Hostage
- Abduction
- Sliding and falling of seafarer during the operation
- Man overboard while checking the anchor command direction
- Injury due to equipment failure
- Eyes and body injuries due to dried mud and rust particulars while anchorage operations
- Damages from anchor chain break
- Electrical shocks from power supply
- Obstructions can be touched to the ship into swinging area
- The valuable cables at the bottom of the sea can be damaged during the anchor weight operation
- Oil spillage
- Damages due to breaking of the lines
- Damages due to rollover of the floating crane on the mother ship by lost of stability
- Damages due to careless usage of the grabs
- Seafarer damage when checking the temperature of the coal on the barge
- Combustions due to high calories of the coal
- Skin and breathing way diseases due to dusty coal operations
- Falling of the seafarers when sweeping the dusts on the hatch coaming
- Dropped the Macgregor type hatch covers into the sea when opening due to heeling
- Damages to the ladders between floating crane and ship due to waving
- Breaking of the lines or damages to the accommodation area parts when shifting of the floating crane
- Damages from dockers such as robbery, wounding, hostage
- Health problems due to prostitute on the ship
- Using the fire for feeding by dockers, staying on deck.
- Damages of the small fishing vessels around the propeller before sailing machinery test.
- Damages such as breaking of lines, break down of the winches and obstructed propeller by lines or nets due to un-controlled pre-test machinery
- Damages harbour or floating crane gangways when they settled on deck due to shifting operation or un-controlled pre-test machinery
- Over trusting of master to the unqualified harbour pilots and leave to control manoeuvre to this unqualified pilots
- To be drunken of the master when ship manoeuvring

The evaluations and rank levels of these risks are determined by FMEA technique. According to this method, some risks are identified in high level category. Except the piracy, hijacking and terror attacks, the whole levels were decreased to an acceptable category via additional measures. The high level risk results are listed below:

- Piracy, hijacking and terror attacks
- Seafarer damage when checking the temperature of the coal on the barge
- Falling of the seafarers when sweeping the dusts on the hatch coaming

- Damages to the ladders between floating crane and ship due to waving
- Breaking of the lines or damages to the accommodation area parts when shifting of the floating crane
- Health problems due to prostitute on the ship
- Over trusting of master to the unqualified harbour pilots and leave to control manoeuvre to this unqualified pilots
- To be drunken of the master when ship manoeuvring

The “piracy, hijacking and terror attacks” risks are examined with Fault Tree Analyses in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2 HERE

When the level of the “piracy, hijacking and terror attacks” risk is examined, it is determined that the frequency of the risk is too high. For this reason, it is come out that new precautions are to be taken. The new precautions are determined as below:

1. Precaution: To establish camera system on deck and mean of access
2. Precaution: To establish sensor lighting system on deck and mean of access
3. Precaution: To rig razor wire around the ship
4. Precaution: To increase the number of watchkeepers
5. Precaution: To hire armed guards
6. Precaution: To establish an alarm system into the stores
7. Precaution: To put on a grate on anchor hole and locking with shackle

DECISION MAKING IN THE RISK MANAGEMENT MODEL

The company management is supposed to decide about which precaution is to be applied. The elimination should be done according to some parameters. The goal is to determine the optimum measure to be taken. The alternatives for reaching

the goal are listed above. Below are the criterions or the parameters for evaluating the alternatives:

- 1- Occupational Health
- 2- Occupational Safety
- 3- Security
- 4- Environment
- 5- Cost
- 6- Quality
- 7- Practicability

A model for company management is established with these alternatives and criterions for taking a decision under the uncertainty. The priority matrix of each criterion and all measures for each criterion are established respectively. The judgments of each pairwise comparison of the elements are made based on the Thomas Saaty’s fundamental scale of absolute numbers as given in the Table 2.

TABLES 3-5 HERE

Based on the questionnaire made with 13 masters of various types of the ships, 2 managers of shipping company, 3 academic staffs in maritime departments which makes 18 experts in total, the measure to be taken is determined as “locking the anchor hole with shackle” in Table 4.

Due to the low cost criterion, “locking the anchor hole with shackle” is also the most-chosen measure in the daily life of the ship industry. The choice of the daily life of the ship industry is corresponded with the model results, which confirms that the model works properly.

CONCLUSION

Herewith this paper work, well-operated risk management system for ship management system is established as per Maritime Labour Convention. According to the Regulation 4.3 in MCL, the shipping companies have a duty to ensure that all shipboard operations are carried safely and affectively by assessing all identified risks to its ship, personnel, environment and business activity and establish appropriate safeguards. The risk

assessments will address the hazards faced in the routine course of personnel duties.

FMEA, FTA and AHP techniques are found suitable for this management system and their suitability is checked by a scenario analyses. The results of the findings are found remarkable and factual. The risks identification for the case study is operated by using the questionnaire and observation methods. 33 main risks are determined for anchoring operation for Samarinda. When these risks are analyzed by FMEA, some risks are diagnosed in the high level category. Except the "piracy, hijacking and terror attacks" risk, the whole levels of the other risks were decreased to an acceptable category via additional measures. However, the level of the "piracy, hijacking and terror attacks" risk cannot be decreased due to the scenario in the study. According to the scenario, the anchorage area is selected Samarinda, Indonesia. GISIS reports show that this area is the densest piracy incident area and because of the density of the attacks the probability factor is always at the top level.

Due to the high significance of the "piracy, hijacking and terror attacks" risk, more detailed analysis were needed. Herein, FTA method is used for finding the roots of the operation. The height of the freeboard, area piracy facility rate, the careless of the personnel are determined as the main reasons. Professional competency of personals is come into prominence at the bottom in Figure 2.

After the all details of the risk and anchorage operation examined and the roots of the incidents are determined, the extra precautions are investigated. The experts in the shipping industry are consulted for opinion on these additional measures. Several explanations have been offered; and seven new hedges have been investigated. Incidentally, the specifications of each precaution is totally different then the other from the point of costs, quality, safety etc. Then the differ points are needed to be determined, seven criteria is obtained by same techniques.

In the Table 3, the comparison matrix of the criteria is presented based on AHP. It can be seen from the table that the most important differ point is calculated as "Occupational Health" and stand in

line as "Occupational Safety", "Security", "Environment", "Quality", "Cost", "Practicability".

The result matrix of the AHP application is constituted in Table 5. From the table, it is apparent that the seventh precaution named as "Putting a grate up to anchor hole and locking with shackle" is calculated as optimum choice. This finding is consistent with the experts contention that the gradation of the "cost" criteria is deceitful. Although the sorting of the "cost" criteria is second to last, the determinant criteria is also observed as same.

The conclusions of the study demonstrate that the results of the model are coincide with daily ship industry applications.

After the all applications were carried out, it is found out that established risk management model in this paper works properly and this model is a good reference for ship management system as per Regulation 4.3. in MLC (2006).

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APPENDIX

Table 1. The Number of Deficiencies Related With MLC Regulations between 20 August 2013 and 31 December 2014

MLC Regulation	Title	Number of Deficiencies
4.3	Health and safety protection and accident prevention	985
3.1	Accommodation and recreational facilities	409
3.2	Food and catering	358
2.1	Seafarers' Employment Agreement	138
2.3	Working hours and resting hours	88
2.2	Wages	56
1.4	Recruitment and placement	31
5.1.3	Maritime labour certificate and declaration of maritime labour observance	24
4.1	Health benefit on board ship and ashore	12
5.1.5	On-board delation procedures	11
5.1.1	Flag State liabilities, General guidelines	9
2.4	Entitlement to leave	6
2.5	Repatriation	4
1.2	Medical Certificate	4
1.3	Training and qualifications	1
Total		2136

Table 2. The definition and explanation of the priority levels.

Priority Levels	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal Importance	Two activities contribute equally to the objective
2	Weak or slight	
3	Moderate Importance	Experience and judgement slightly favour one activity over another
4	Moderate Plus	
5	Strong Importance	Experience and judgement strongly favour one activity over another
6	Strong Plus	
7	Very Strong of Demonstrated Importance	An activity is favoured very strongly over another, its dominance demonstrated in practice
8	Very, very strong	
9	Extreme Importance	The evidence favouring one activity over another is of the highest possible order of affirmation.

Table3.Comparison of Criteria's Between Each Other

Normalised Matrix	O. Health	O. Safety	Quality	Environment	Cost	Security	Practicability	Priority Level
O. Health	0,31	0,28	0,29	0,32	0,37	0,34	0,27	0,3127
O. Safety	0,26	0,23	0,26	0,22	0,16	0,25	0,17	0,2199
Quality	0,07	0,06	0,06	0,04	0,11	0,07	0,10	0,0745
Environment	0,11	0,12	0,19	0,11	0,13	0,08	0,15	0,1282
Cost	0,05	0,09	0,03	0,05	0,06	0,07	0,08	0,0625
Security	0,13	0,13	0,12	0,21	0,13	0,14	0,16	0,1455
Practicability	0,07	0,08	0,04	0,05	0,05	0,05	0,06	0,0568
Total	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00

Table 4.The Matrix of Evaluationsof Precautions for Each Criteria's

O. Health	1. Precaution	2. Precaution	3. Precaution	4. Precaution	5. Precaution	6. Precaution	7. Precaution	Priority Level
1. Precaution	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,1598
2. Precaution	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,1418
3. Precaution	0,10	0,10	0,10	0,10	0,10	0,10	0,10	0,0994
4. Precaution	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,1496
5. Precaution	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,1497
6. Precaution	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,1461
7. Precaution	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,1535
TOPLAM								1,00

O. Safety	1. Precaution	2. Precaution	3. Precaution	4. Precaution	5. Precaution	6. Precaution	7. Precaution	Priority Level
1. Precaution	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,1514
2. Precaution	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,1232
3. Precaution	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,1158
4. Precaution	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,1458
5. Precaution	0,17	0,17	0,17	0,17	0,17	0,17	0,17	0,1669
6. Precaution	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,1487
7. Precaution	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,1481
TOPLAM								1,00

Quality	1. Precaution	2. Precaution	3. Precaution	4. Precaution	5. Precaution	6. Precaution	7. Precaution	Priority Level
1. Precaution	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,1439
2. Precaution	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,1404
3. Precaution	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,1143
4. Precaution	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,1382
5. Precaution	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,1569
6. Precaution	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,1609
7. Precaution	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,1454
TOPLAM								1,00

Environment	1. Precaution	2. Precaution	3. Precaution	4. Precaution	5. Precaution	6. Precaution	7. Precaution	Priority Level
1. Precaution	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,1542
2. Precaution	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,1548
3. Precaution	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,0903
4. Precaution	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,1639
5. Precaution	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,16	0,1573
6. Precaution	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,1395
7. Precaution	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,1399
TOPLAM								1,00

Cost	1. Precaution	2. Precaution	3. Precaution	4. Precaution	5. Precaution	6. Precaution	7. Precaution	Priority Level
1. Precaution	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,0792
2. Precaution	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,0932
3. Precaution	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,1408
4. Precaution	0,22	0,22	0,22	0,22	0,22	0,22	0,22	0,2223
5. Precaution	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,08	0,0834
6. Precaution	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,09	0,0937
7. Precaution	0,29	0,29	0,29	0,29	0,29	0,29	0,29	0,2873
TOPLAM								1,00

Security	1. Precaution	2. Precaution	3. Precaution	4. Precaution	5. Precaution	6. Precaution	7. Precaution	Priority Level
1. Precaution	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,1415
2. Precaution	0,13	0,13	0,13	0,13	0,13	0,13	0,13	0,1271
3. Precaution	0,13	0,13	0,13	0,13	0,13	0,13	0,13	0,1340
4. Precaution	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,1368
5. Precaution	0,17	0,17	0,17	0,17	0,17	0,17	0,17	0,1739
6. Precaution	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,1410
7. Precaution	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,1456
TOPLAM								1,00

Practicability	1. Precaution	2. Precaution	3. Precaution	4. Precaution	5. Precaution	6. Precaution	7. Precaution	Priority Level
1. Precaution	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,1063
2. Precaution	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,1115
3. Precaution	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,1137
4. Precaution	0,18	0,18	0,18	0,18	0,18	0,18	0,18	0,1817
5. Precaution	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,15	0,1497
6. Precaution	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,12	0,1222
7. Precaution	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,21	0,2150
TOPLAM								1,00

Table 5. The Results Matrix of AHP Application

Priority of the Criterias	0,3127	0,2199	0,0745	0,1282	0,0625	0,1455	0,0568	
Criteria	O. Health	O. Safety	Quality	Environment	Cost	Security	Practicability	
Camera System	0,1598	0,1514	0,1439	0,1542	0,0792	0,1415	0,1063	0,1453
Lighting System	0,1418	0,1232	0,1404	0,1548	0,0932	0,1271	0,1115	0,1324
Razor Wire	0,0994	0,1158	0,1143	0,0903	0,1408	0,1340	0,1137	0,1114
Watchkeeping number	0,1496	0,1458	0,1382	0,1639	0,2223	0,1368	0,1817	0,1543

Armed Guards	0,1497	0,1669	0,1569	0,1573	0,0834	0,1739	0,1497	0,1544
Alarms System	0,1461	0,1487	0,1609	0,1395	0,0937	0,1410	0,1222	0,1416
Put on a grate up to anchor hole and locking with shackle	0,1535	0,1481	0,1454	0,1399	0,2873	0,1456	0,2150	0,1607

Figure 1. Risk Management Flow Chart

Figure 2. Fault Tree Analysis for Anchoring in the Piracy Area